

MECHANICAL TESTING AND FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF LATTICE STRUCTURE FUSELAGE PROTOTYPE

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ABSTRACT

Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) composite structures are becoming increasingly used in the aerospace industry mainly due to their high strength to weight ratio. A wet filament winding carbon fibre lattice structure can offer desirable highly tailored properties for applications such as fuselage sections in commercial and business airplanes. In this work a scaled down prototype of a fuselage section designed and developed as part of the EC project WASIS was tested under bending loads to evaluate its mechanical response and validate the developed Finite Element (FE) models. Testing was performed under pure bending load up to an approximate 30 kN-m moment. The aim was to load the fuselage and record the resulting strains in order to validate the stiffness of the FE model but not to cause any failure to the prototype. A satisfactory correlation between experimental data and simulations was found, which enables the use of the FE model for analysis and design optimisation of the fuselage structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

For many years the aerospace industry used all-aluminium semi-monocoque structures to manufacture an aircraft's fuselage. The loads experienced by a fuselage structure include but not limited to the external loading from the engine, wings, empennage, air turbulences as well as internal loads caused by the pressurised cabin. To provide the mechanical strength for carrying these loads a series of frames and stringers were used to strengthen the skin [1]. However, the increasing fuel prices in line with new more strict environmental regulations on greenhouse gases dictated the move towards a lighter structure for aircraft designs to maximize efficiency and reduce the cost in order to keep air transport competitive and safe. CFRP composites have high values of specific strength and rigidity, which potentially can make them a preferred candidate for use as aluminium replacement. However, replacing the aluminium frame-stringer stiffened structure without design modification would only provide a weight saving of 10–20% [2]. Taking into account the higher specific strength and rigidity of CFRP compared to aluminium (up to $\times 3$ and $\times 6$, respectively) [3], and the possibility of tailoring the mechanical properties of the anisotropic composite it can be concluded that the potential of CFRPs has not been completely realised using the conventional aircraft airframe design and layouts. To achieve the full capacity of the composites in weight and cost saving the composite structure should fulfil the following requirements [4]:

1. The principal load bearing composite element must have a unidirectional (UD) structure;
2. The manufacturing process has to have the potential of full automation and to provide a completely integral structure.

The UD composite only works under uniaxial loading hence the anisogrid structures developed about 30 years ago and widely used in rocket launchers and spacecraft structures might be a suitable candidate [5]. These structures consist of ribs either helically or ring shaped made of unidirectional fibre reinforced composites using automatic filament winding. The majority of load, including bending moments, torques and transverse forces, are carried out by the ribs, while the skin carries an insignificant part of the loading (internal pressure and aerodynamic loads) and transfers them to the ribs.

An attempt to design and manufacture such a lattice structure with the intention to replace a section of a conventional fuselage structure was made under the framework of project FP7-265549 WASIS (Composite Fuselage Section Wafer Design Approach for Safety Increasing in Worst Case Situations and Joints Minimizing, <http://www.wasis.eu>). Wet filament winding was selected as the appropriate method combining continuous carbon fibre (HTS40 (12K)-F13) and epoxy resin (Araldite LY556 / Hardener 917 / Accelerator DY070).

Because of the prime use of the lattice type structures being in rocket launchers and spacecraft part, most of the experimental data on structural validation available are for compression loading [4]. In contrast to the above, a fuselage structure will experience a wide range of loads from a number of different sources. The weight of the fuselage and payload cause downwards bending around the wings putting the fuselage's top in tension and the bottom in compression. During negative g-maneuvres, some of these loads are reversed. In addition, bending loads during take-off and landing are significant. Hence in this work we have tested a filament wound carbon fibre lattice composite structure in pure bending and used the experimental data to validate the developed FE models that would then enable the prediction of the structure's response to various loading conditions.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Structure Description

A schematic representation of the lattice structure is presented in Figure 1. The structure is 2 m long, 1.8 m in diameter and comprises a number of spiral (i.e., helical) and hoop ribs with trapezoidal cross section. The composite structure is manufactured in a single process with the spiral rib intersections at the edges of the section acting as the turning points in the winding. Metallic attachments are fitted at these intersection points to enable the load transfer from one section to another.

Figure 1: Schematic of the designed lattice fuselage section

2.2 Article Test Preparation

Pre-test preparation was performed on the metallic hinges located at the spiral rib intersections of the structure to insure proper transfer of the applied load to the fuselage section. The metallic hinges were taken off, grit blasted and then adhesively bonded before fastened back to the structure. Photographs in Figure 2 present the sequence of the aforementioned preparation.

Figure 2: Pre-test preparation of the load carrying members

2.3 Assembling

FE analysis was used to design the test fixture. The objective was to build a test fixture, which would have sufficient stiffness and be robust enough to apply the loads without being excessively heavy and complicated to manufacture and transport. Figure 3 shows the geometry and stress results of the final design of the test fixture at an applied load of 75 kN·m.

Figure 3: Finite element analysis of the test fixture

Due to the size and weight of the fixture the assembly of the part required exceptional care to avoid pre-test damage to the structural part. The fuselage section was fitted to one end of the fixture then the

second loading arm of the fixture was lifted, and slowly pushed into place to install the load transferring bolts, which were bonded to the part, into the fixture holes (Figure 4). The horizontal alignment of the part was necessary for defining the initial point of the loading actuators (i.e., zero displacement). To align the part the load transferring bolts at the top of the fuselage section and the connection plate were tightened to a degree that the part edges on top and bottom were flushed with the surface of the plate. Then the part was horizontally levelled using a digital spirit level before sliding in the second fixture arm and the connection plate flushed with the edges of other end of the fuselage.

Figure 4: Assembling the part in the test fixture

2.4 Loading

The fuselage section was subjected to bending in order to measure its deformation response, and use the collected data to validate the created FE models. The load was applied via constant displacement of the actuators located at each end of the lever arm of the test fixture. An overview of the load application setup is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Load application fixture

The bending load was applied to the part by constant displacement of 0.75 mm/min at the end of the lever arm (Figure 6) using the hydraulic powered actuators. The two actuators were synchronised and their load-displacement curves were recorded separately (Figure 7).

Figure 6: Assembly of the fuselage in the test fixture

From the graphs in Figure 7 it is evident that the two actuators were 100% synchronized in displacement (i.e., displacement control test), but the load response of the structure was slightly different at each end. The load cell located at the left (far) actuator experienced about 1.8 kN more load than the one on the right (near) actuator during the test.

Figure 7: Displacement-time and load-time graphs of the actuators at each end of the fixture

2.5 Deformation

Several strain gauges were attached to different parts of the fuselage to monitor and record the deformation caused by the load. The location of the strain gauges is presented in Figure 8. Since the aim of the test was to obtain load-strain data and validate the developed FE models, the part was only loaded to a pre-defined level and then unloaded to avoid any failures. The obtained load-strain graphs are presented in Figure 9 and Figure 10. The recorded strain values were as expected; with the fuselage experiencing tension on the top, compression on the bottom and almost no longitudinal strains on the sides. This proves that the specimen was loaded fairly uniformly. Similar trend was found for the strain gauges located on the ribs at the top and bottom of the fuselage. The strain values were recorded during both the loading and unloading part of the test. From the collected data it is

evident that nearly all the accumulated strain in the loading phase was removed in the unloading step and loading-unloading strain curves are overlapping. This verifies that no local damage occurred in the test around the measurement areas.

Figure 8: Schematic of strain gauge locations on the fuselage

Figure 9: Load-strain curves of the skin; (O: outer surface, I: inner surface, T: top, B: bottom, S: sides)

Figure 10: Load-strain curves of the ribs (locations as presented in Figure 8)

Digital Image Correlation (DIC) was used to record the deformation of a bigger area compared to the strain gauges. The area covered was a square 300mm × 300mm on the top of the fuselage. For measuring the displacement with the DIC a special pattern was required. The pattern had a white background with different sizes of black dots and was produced using spray paint. Figure 11 shows the setup of DIC equipment relative to the part and fixture.

Figure 11: DIC setup for strain measurements

Figure 12 presents the strain data obtained from DIC for the area around the location of the top strain gauge. The axis directions are as follows: X is parallel to the fuselage axis; Y is in the tangential plane that passes through the point of strain gauge location normal to the plane that goes through the fuselage axis and the strain gauge location; Z is the radial axis of the fuselage going through the strain gauge location. The frequency of measurement was 1 picture every 10 second and a total of 159 measurements were performed with the 159th being at the maximum load.

Figure 12: Strain values measured by DIC in X and Y directions

An interesting feature seen in Figure 12 is that the skin attached to the ribs experienced nearly half the strain measured in other parts of the skin, this can be seen by bluish colour of these locations compared to the green background. This implies directly that the location of the ribs is visible in the strain map of the surface (i.e., dotted line in Figure 12 a). The line with no data available (i.e., gray line) is where the strain gauge wire was located.

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The model of the scaled fuselage section prototype that was constructed didn't contain the geometry of the test fixture. Instead, the bending moments were applied directly to the structure ends by MPC constraints with a reference point located 355 mm from the cylinder edge as shown in Figure 13. The position of the reference point corresponds to the position of the test fixture's pin around which the loading arm rotates.

Figure 13: Scaled fuselage section loading

The structure was modelled with conventional shell elements. The global size of the elements of the skin was 5 mm; however, the ribs were modelled with four elements across the height. The mesh used in the FE model is shown in Figure 14. The ribs cross-section was simulated with constant thickness of 4 mm.

Figure 14: Scaled fuselage section model mesh

The comparison of axial and hoop strains obtained by DIC and FE analysis is shown in Figure 15 and Figure 16. A satisfactory correlation was achieved and the level of strain was very similar between the model and the experiment.

Figure 15: Axial strain comparison between DIC and FEA

Figure 16: Hoop strain comparison between DIC and FEA

When comparing the strain gauges measurements with local strains predicted by FE analysis, there was a noticeable difference between the top and the bottom of the cylinder section as shown in Figure 17. The strains predicted by the model in tension agreed very well with the experiment; however, the compressive strains at the bottom were found to be lower in the simulations. This applies for both the

skin and the ribs. This difference is caused by the modelling idealisation and application of the load by MPC constraints in the model. In reality the loads are transferred differently in the tension and compression sections of the structure. The compression at the bottom of the cylinder is applied by all the surfaces coming in contact with the test fixture plate, while the tensile loads at the top are transferred mainly through the ribs bolted to the fixture plate by integrated pins.

Figure 17: FEA-experiment strain correlation for ribs at bottom

The scaled fuselage section was not tested until destruction and only a small amount of the load carrying capacity was applied. The maximum bending moment applied during the test was 29 kN·m. The analysis suggested that the failure indices, when using the material allowables, were around 0.16 at this level of applied bending moment. Figure 18 shows a contour of the Tsai-Wu failure criterion at an applied bending moment of 35 kN·m. This figure also indicates that possible failure locations would be around the areas where the helical ribs join at cylinder's edges, if higher load was to be applied during the test.

Figure 18: Tsai-Wu failure criterion

4 CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions could be derived from the experimental work and FE model validation. The lattice structure of the fuselage section has not experienced any damage during the loading-unloading cycle as the load-strain graphs were found to overlap. The difference seen between the strain levels experienced by the free skin and skin attached to the ribs suggests that a possible debonding between the skin and ribs may occur if ultimate loading scenarios are applied. Hence special attention has to be made for design and manufacturing these connections. Finally, the developed FE model was successfully validated against the experimental results and could be used to predict future modifications of the structure, hence to assist with reducing the requirement for testing of the structure.

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